

Application form: Open Science Infrastructure (2024) - full proposal

Section 1: Applicants

Name of the main applicant	Dr. Eline Oppersma
Affiliation – institution	University of Twente
Affiliation – department	Cardiovascular and Respiratory Physiology
Position	Assistant professor
End date of contract	Permanent position
Guarantee needed & added yes/no/n.a.	n.a.
E-mail address	e.oppersma@utwente.nl
ORCID ID	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0150-306X

Name of the co-applicant	Dr. Annemijn Jonkman
Affiliation – institution	Erasmus medical center
Affiliation – department	Department of Intensive Care
Position	Assistant professor
End date of contract	Permanent position
Guarantee added yes/no/n.a.	n.a.
E-mail address	a.jonkman@erasmusmc.nl
ORCID ID	https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8778-5135

Name of the subcontractor	Netherlands eScience Center
E-mail address	info@esciencecenter.nl
Organisation	Netherlands eScience Center

Section 2: Summary

Proposed project title	Multimodal Monitoring of the Respiratory System: an integrated analysis platform (M3Resp)
Project duration (in months)	12 months

English public summary	
<p>Mechanical ventilation is an essential and potentially lifesaving support strategy for 40.000 critically ill patients in the Netherlands annually. However, outdated and inadequate closed-source software hampers effective respiratory monitoring. We propose M3Resp: an open-source software platform for MultiModal Monitoring of the Respiratory system. M3Resp will focus on bedside techniques, such as electrical impedance tomography (EIT) for imaging of lung ventilation and perfusion, and surface electromyography (sEMG) to monitor electrical activity of the respiratory muscles. M3Resp will promote open science, and enable cutting-edge research that is accessible and adaptable, to directly impact clinical practice for Intensive Care physicians and patients.</p>	
Word count EN-SUM (max 100): 99	

Dutch public summary

Kunstmatige beademing biedt cruciale en potentieel levensreddende ademhalingsondersteuning voor 40.000 ernstig zieke patiënten in Nederland per jaar. Verouderde en ongeschikte software belemmert echter effectieve ademhalingsmonitoring. Wij introduceren M3Resp: een open-source softwareplatform voor MultiModale Monitoring van het ademhalingssysteem. M3Resp zal zich richten op technieken aan bed, zoals elektrische impedantietomografie (EIT) voor beeldvorming van de ventilatie en perfusie van de longen, en oppervlakte elektromyografie (sEMG) om de elektrische activiteit van de ademhalingsspieren te monitoren. M3Resp zal open wetenschap bevorderen en baanbrekend onderzoek mogelijk maken, dat toegankelijk en flexibel toepasbaar is. Hiermee maken wij klinische impact voor intensive care zorgverleners en patiënten.

Word count NL-SUM (max 100): 99

Section 3: Alignment with the scope of the call

3.1 Vision for the project and alignment with the aim of this call

Mechanical ventilation is vital for acute and chronic respiratory failure, supporting ~40.000 patients in the Netherlands annually. However, outdated closed-source software limits effective monitoring. Our **Multimodal Monitoring of the Respiratory system (M3Resp)** software aims to integrate respiratory monitoring techniques from two previously developed open-source platforms: [ALIVE](#) for electrical impedance tomography (EIT) and [ReSurfEMG](#) for surface electromyography (sEMG) [1]. Our versatile, user-friendly software will promote open science and enable cutting-edge research by handling multiple data formats, consistent processing, and storing outputs according to FAIR standards. M3Resp will remain adaptable for integrating emerging modalities, ensuring long-term utility and impact on clinical research and practice. We will ensure full transparency of underlying code, protocols, and methodologies, adhering to community-based standards for seamless integration and interoperability. Engaging existing user-communities of ALIVE and ReSurfEMG will guide new developments, making M3Resp a modernized, accessible, and impactful toolkit that advances open science and data-driven respiratory clinical research.

Word count SEC31 (max. 150): 150

3.2 User communities, challenges and needs

We address a crucial community need to effectively monitor, process, and analyze life-saving medical data, while simultaneously improving software and digital competence. Respiratory data suffers from several challenges, including dependence on vendor-specific closed-source tools and data formats, and a lack of standardized metadata and analysis pipelines. This limits reproducibility and implementation of data-driven research. With accessible, user-friendly and scientifically grounded software, M3Resp contributes to interoperability of digital solutions by processing all existing data formats and converting them to standard data types. These data can be analyzed equivalently and in parallel, which is not possible with any existing tool. We have already fostered vividly interacting (inter)national communities of users and developers around our previous software, via Lorentz center workshops [2,3], focusing on lung EIT with ALIVE, and respiratory muscle sEMG with ReSurfEMG. We have gathered and published professional community recommendations for standardized use/processing of EIT and sEMG data [4,5] and received substantial endorsement from private partners. Early-stage community input serves as a foundation for further development. Community-driven expansion of data types and sharable processing/analysis pipelines will be facilitated by providing clear tutorials. We will build M3Resp with the clear goal to cater to all life-scientists working with physiological/clinical time-series data.

Word count SEC32 (max. 200): 199

3.3 Alignment of project with OS principles

M3Resp will provide a modernized open-source, transparent data processing toolkit, easily accessible to researchers with a wide-ranging digital skillset. This will lead to FAIRification of a currently highly closed-format data type, allowing for more sustainable and reproducible research and sharable workflows for data processing and analysis. As a community-driven platform from the get-go, it will be paramount to adopt good collaborative coding standards during the development of M3Resp. We are dedicated to setting the right example for this and working in close collaboration with our community to help them develop the required skills. Furthermore, we will create clear and comprehensible developer's documentation, guidelines, and tutorials as a resource for less-experienced programmers. M3Resp will also open a path to using respiratory data for federated machine learning, with no effort required to harmonize the data. With our ALIVE software, our team's commitment to setting a new standard for open, reproducible, and responsible research in healthcare innovation was recognized with the 2024 Open and Responsible Science award of the Erasmus University Rotterdam. With M3Resp, we are dedicated to continuing to make a clinical impact and advancing digital competencies across the life-science community.

Word count SEC33 (max. 200): 189

Section 4: Feasibility

4.1 Project plan

This project consists of the following 5 work packages (WPs).

WP1: Initiation Phase

Prior to the project's start, a vacancy will be drafted to attract two Python-skilled postdoctoral researchers with expertise in signal analysis, sEMG and/or EIT. In the initial phase, a kick-off meeting with all stakeholders will be organized, to define project goals and deliverables, roles and responsibilities, develop a detailed project timeline, and set up project management tools and communication channels. Next, postdoctoral researchers will become acquainted with the current software.

WP2: Requirement Analysis and Design

ALIVE and ReSurfEMG were developed as two independent software packages. ALIVE implements a strong data handling structure, while ReSurfEMG includes a wealth of algorithms for signal processing and feature calculation. As these packages interact with essentially similar data (in terms of structure, dimensionality, etc.), they could mutually benefit from each other's strengths – boosting interoperability and reusability of the data and software.

In preparing the merge, detailed requirements and existing software architecture will be analyzed. Mapping of similarities and differences between these packages is important to define ultimate data formats, processing pipelines and user interface requirements for M3Resp. We will consult Health-RI on implementing FAIR data and metadata standards.

WP3: Merging ALIVE and ReSurfEMG into M3Resp

To merge the two core modules, we will first add a dedicated container for sEMG data using ALIVE's data handling structure. Next, we will port the algorithms for sEMG processing and analysis from ReSurfEMG into M3Resp, ensuring their applicability on all relevant data. Finally, to ensure proper interoperability, we will create algorithms to synchronize the different data streams. Ultimately, this will lead to a unified platform for all major respiratory monitoring data formats with a rich processing and analysis toolkit. As data complexity grows, we will develop standardized and sharable pre- and postprocessing pipelines for different kinds of data. This allows the user to optimize and accelerate the processing of large volumes of data in a reproducible manner.

In parallel, we will focus on interpretation and visualization tools for end-users without programming experience. ALIVE and ReSurfEMG already initiated the development of two separate code-free graphic user interfaces (GUIs), allowing researchers to avoid the codebase to use the software. We will start development of a single versatile GUI for M3Resp. The input from the community and early testing by its members during the development will continuously guide GUI development, guaranteeing its adherence to user needs.

Continuous testing is a pillar weaved throughout WP3, to integrate all modules and conduct comprehensive testing of separate units, integrated units, and the full system.

WP4: Expansion of M3Resp

An important objective of M3Resp is to realize time-series data processing from any device. Dedicated containers exist for sEMG and EIT, while associated data are handled by generic containers for continuous, sparse, or interval-associated data. Only minor adaptations to this structure are required to handle any time-series data. We plan to expand the set of dedicated data containers to other vital respiratory monitoring modalities (e.g., ventilator waveforms, respiratory muscle pressure, etc.).

WP5: Community engagement

Leveraging our well-established ReSurfEMG and ALIVE networks (accomplished through two successful Lorentz workshops and ongoing collaborations), we will gather invaluable early-stage input on software criteria, including (meta)data types/formats and testing. We are dedicated to building a robust user-community for M3Resp via multiple strategies:

- **Lowering the Adoption Barrier:** We will involve researchers from medical centers across the Netherlands to gain visibility and local expertise via user-friendly and easy to access software, facilitating adoption of M3Resp.
- **Tutorials and Documentation:** We will create (video) tutorials to guide users to implement M3Resp to their own data or to sample data that we will make freely available. For the Python API, we will create Jupyter notebooks outlining common analysis pipelines, and cookiecutters as project templates. In addition, we will provide extensive and comprehensible user and developer documentation.
- **Dissemination:** M3Resp will be published as a dedicated software publication, e.g. in the Journal of Open-Source Software, allowing for in-depth external review and quality assessment. Furthermore, M3Resp will be cited as output in our high-ranked research publications, spreading its visibility in the wider professional community. We intend to present M3Resp at conferences (software-focused and research-oriented) and will maintain active communication with the community through mailings, ensuring dissemination within the clinical research community.

WP	Task	Month											
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1	Hire staff												
	Kick-off meeting												
2	Review existing software												
	Define requirements												
3	Merge datahandling												
	Merge algorithms												
	Visualization and GUI												
	Testing												
4	Modality expansion												
5	Community input												
	Tutorials and documentation												
	Dissemination												

Word count SEC41 (max. 750): 749

4.2 Team composition

Name, surname	Affiliation	Expertise	Role/contributions
Dr. E. (Eline) Oppersma	UTwente	Advanced analysis of sEMG data	Project manager, leader of ReSurfEMG, innovative data approaches and transparent software development
Dr. A. (Annemijn) Jonkman	Erasmus MC	Advanced analysis of EIT data	Project leader of ALIVE, focusing on EIT, testing and community engagement
P. (Peter) Somhorst, MSc	Erasmus MC	ICU data analysis and software development	Project member ALIVE, time-series data processing, software development
To be hired – postdoc	UTwente	Time-series data analysis, Python	Software and GUI developer, focusing on sEMG and merging modalities to M3Resp
To be hired – postdoc	Erasmus MC	Time-series data analysis, Python	Software and GUI developer, focusing on EIT and merging modalities to M3Resp
To be contracted – Research Software Engineer	NLeSC	Software structure and development	Software development consultancy

Section 5: Sustainability and software management

Section 5.1: Sustainability plan

Outcomes that need to be sustained include the software code that is released free and open source, along with all relevant documentation, tutorials and publications. The core research teams at the University of Twente and Erasmus Medical Center, consisting of technical physician-scientists with programming and engineering expertise, have and will have in the future all necessary skills to maintain and improve the software after the project ends. Furthermore, they can support the broader community that uses it, by including and updating deliverables (e.g. user-instructions, notebooks) as needed.

Based on our continuing efforts and (inter)national network commitments to the ReSurfEMG and ALIVE software and their users, we are confident that the M3Resp tool will be widely adopted across institutional, national and disciplinary borders. This will accelerate existing and create new scientific and clinical collaborations as well as (inter)national multi-center studies, further expanding the community around the software and ensuring long-term sustainability. The modular and dynamic design of M3Resp allows for the incorporation of new data modalities and algorithms, including machine learning techniques for time-series analysis, which is crucial for its ongoing relevance. By continuously engaging with the community and incorporating their feedback, we will ensure M3Resp remains relevant and effective in meeting the continuously evolving needs of researchers and clinicians.

The plan to secure resources is built on collaborations with the community and industry. Leveraging our strong interdisciplinary network, we will promote thorough use of the software within a broad (inter-)national research and clinical community. This will help to further develop the software and stimulate its longevity. If significant financial resources are needed after the project ends, we will incorporate funding for M3Resp developments within ongoing research projects/grants utilizing the software as a key tool for data analyses. Lastly, our close contacts with relevant industrial partners will also result in mutual interests to further develop the software towards clinical implementation as part of commercially available monitoring devices.

Word count SEC51 (max 300): 292

Section 5.2: Software management plan

1. Please provide a brief description of your software, stating its purpose and intended audience.

M3Resp is designed to integrate and enhance respiratory monitoring techniques by combining features from two open-source platforms, ALIVE and ReSurfEMG. It provides real-time bedside information, processes multiple data formats consistently, and stores outputs according to FAIR standards. The software aims to promote open science, facilitate cutting-edge research, and support clinical practice by offering a versatile, user-friendly toolkit for respiratory data analysis.

M3Resp is intended for a clinical audience, including researchers, clinicians, and healthcare professionals involved in respiratory monitoring and analysis. It is also suitable for technical physician-scientists, engineers, and developers who are interested in open-source software and data-driven respiratory research. The software is designed to be accessible to users with varying levels of digital skillsets, from those with programming experience to those who prefer code-free command line interfaces and eventually a GUI dashboard functionality.

2. How will you manage versioning of your software?

Versioning of M3Resp will be effected using GitHub's version control features. Each change to the codebase will be tracked using git, allowing us to maintain a detailed history of modifications. We will follow semantic versioning (e.g., v1.0.0) to clearly indicate major, minor, and patch updates.

To ensure consistency, git tags will be used to mark specific releases and milestones. Additionally, branches for different stages of development will be created, such as 'main' for stable releases and 'develop' for ongoing work. Pull requests will be used to review and merge changes, ensuring that each update is thoroughly vetted before being integrated into the main codebase. Importantly, the main branch will be protected by requiring review from member(s) of the community before merging pull requests.

3. How will you make your software publicly available? What licence will your software have?

M3Resp will be hosted on GitHub, in a public repository, allowing anyone to clone, fork, or download it, under the Apache 2.0 license.

4. How will users of your software be able to cite your software?

We will register our software with Zenodo, a platform that assigns a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) to the repository. This DOI can be used in academic papers and other publications to provide a permanent and citable link to the software. Users will be able to cite our software by referencing the Zenodo record. A citation format will be provided in the repository's README file, including contributing author(s), name of the software, the specific version being cited, the URL to the GitHub repository and the date of the version release.

5. How will your software be documented? Please describe your plans for: user documentation, documentation for future developers and for installation requirements. Please provide links to documentation if already available.

Our software will be thoroughly documented to ensure ease of use and future development. The documentation will be divided into three main sections. First there will be user documentation, provided in the GitHub README file and including an overview of the software, its features, and a primer on how to use it. More detailed user guides, tutorials, and FAQs will be hosted on readthedocs.com or github.io. This will help users understand how to get the most out of the software.

Second, documentation for (future) developers will be included in a 'Contributing' section in the GitHub repository outlining how developers can contribute to the project. This will cover coding standards, branching strategies, and how to submit pull requests. Lastly, the README file will include a section on installation requirements, detailing the dependencies and steps needed to install the software. We will also provide a requirements.txt file for Python dependencies, ensuring that users can easily set up the software in their environment.

6. How will contribution guidelines and governance structure of your software be documented?

The software's contribution guidelines and governance structure will be clearly documented to ensure transparency and encourage community involvement.

The CONTRIBUTING.md file in the GitHub repository will outline how contributors can get involved. This will cover forking and creating new branches, coding standards and best practices, submitting a pull request and the review process, and guidelines for reporting issues and suggesting features.

The GOVERNANCE.md file in the GitHub repository will document the governance structure. This will include roles and responsibilities of core team members and maintainers, decision-making processes, including how major changes are proposed, discussed, and approved, a code of conduct to ensure a respectful and collaborative environment and information on meetings or communication channels for contributors.

7. How will your software be tested?

Built-in test functions will be obligatory for all new contributions. Contributors will be required to write unit tests for any new features or bug fixes they submit. These tests will be included in the codebase and run automatically as part of our continuous integration (CI) pipeline. We will use testing frameworks such as pytest for to facilitate the creation and execution of these tests.

In addition to automated tests, our software will be tested by researchers and maintainers. This will involve manual testing to ensure that the software performs as expected in real-world scenarios. In the README and CONTRIBUTING files, we will encourage researchers to provide feedback on the software's functionality and usability, which will be used to make further improvements.

We will set up a CI pipeline to automatically run tests on every pull request and commit. This will help catch issues early and ensure that the codebase remains stable. The CI pipeline will include checks for code quality, style, and security vulnerabilities, in addition to running the test suite.

8. How will you check that it respects the licences of libraries and dependencies it uses?

The CI pipeline will include steps to run license checks on every build. This ensures that any new dependencies added to the project are automatically checked for license compliance.

A LICENSES.md file in our GitHub repository will list all third-party dependencies and their respective licenses. This file will be updated regularly to reflect any changes in the dependencies used by our software.

9. How will your software be packaged and distributed?

Packaging will be performed using standard and up-to-date Python packaging standards, and published through both PyPi and Conda (Forge). CI pipelines will be made to automatically build and publish new versions.

10. What level of support will be provided for users of the software and how will this support be organised?

We will provide multiple levels of support for users of our software to ensure they have the help they need, and for our community to maintain and expand. Support will be provided via comprehensive documentation on GitHub and ReadTheDocs, including installation guides, usage instructions, and troubleshooting tips. From both ReSurfEMG and ALIVE, vivid communities have developed of researchers working together and keeping close contact on their progress and projects. M3Resp will aim to provide support by using platforms like GitHub Discussions where users can ask questions, share experiences, and help each other. This will foster a collaborative environment and allow users to benefit from the collective knowledge of the community. This includes using the Issues feature in the GitHub repository for users to report bugs, request features, and ask for help. The community that is already started to grow also entails direct email support for personalized assistance and of course the development team could schedule video calls or chat sessions on a case-by-case basis. Lastly, again arising from previous community workshops for the ReSurfEMG and ALIVE projects, we intend to keep users informed about new releases, updates, and important announcements through a mailing list or a dedicated section in the GitHub repository.

11. How do you plan to ensure long term maintenance of your software?

We will sustain the software code as free and open source, along with all relevant documentation, tutorials, and publications. For publications we aim for code presentations as in the Journal of Open Source Software [1] and implementation of the software [6,7]. As described in paragraph 5.1, the core research teams at the University of Twente and Erasmus MC have the necessary skills to maintain and improve the software after the project ends. These teams will support the broader community by updating deliverables, such as user instructions and notebooks, as needed. By continuously engaging with the community and incorporating their feedback, we will ensure M3Resp remains relevant and effective.

Section 6: References

- [1] C.M. Moore, W. Baccinelli, O. Sivokon, R. Simon, P. Warnaar, E. Oppersma, ReSurfEMG: A Python library for preprocessing and analysis of respiratory EMG., *J Open Source Softw* 8 (2023) 5251. <https://doi.org/10.21105/JOSS.05251>.
- [2] E. Oppersma, Surface EMG of respiratory muscles: innovative analyses to daily practice, (n.d.). <https://www.lorentzcenter.nl/surface-emg-of-respiratory-muscles-innovative-analyses-to-daily-practice.html> (accessed March 25, 2025).
- [3] A. Jonkman, EIT during mechanical ventilation: a standardized innovative workflow, (n.d.). <https://www.lorentzcenter.nl/eit-during-mechanical-ventilation-a-standardized-innovative-workflow.html> (accessed March 25, 2025).
- [4] A.H. Jonkman, R.S.P. Warnaar, W. Baccinelli, N.M. Carbon, R.F. D’Cruz, J. Doorduyn, J.L.M. van Doorn, J. Elshof, L. Estrada-Petrocelli, J. Graßhoff, L.M.A. Heunks, A.A. Koopman, D. Langer, C.M. Moore, J.M. Nunez Silveira, E. Petersen, D. Poddighe, M. Ramsay, A. Rodrigues, L.H. Roesthuis, A. Rossel, A. Torres, M.L. Duiverman, E. Oppersma, Analysis and applications of respiratory surface EMG: report of a round table meeting, *Crit Care* 28 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1186/S13054-023-04779-X>.
- [5] G. Scaramuzzo, B. Pavlovsky, A. Adler, W. Baccinelli, D.L. Bodor, L.F. Damiani, G. Franchineau, J. Francovich, I. Frerichs, J.A.S. Giralt, B. Grychtol, H. He, B.H. Katira, A.A. Koopman, S. Leonhardt, L.S. Menga, A. Mousa, M. Pellegrini, T. Piraino, P. Priani, P. Somhorst, E. Spinelli, C. Händel, F. Suárez-Sipmann, J.J. Wisse, T. Becher, A.H. Jonkman, Electrical impedance tomography monitoring in adult ICU patients: state-of-the-art, recommendations for standardized acquisition, processing, and clinical use, and future directions, *Crit Care* 28 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1186/S13054-024-05173-X>.
- [6] J.J. Wisse, G. Scaramuzzo, M. Pellegrini, L. Heunks, T. Piraino, P. Somhorst, L. Brochard, T. Mauri, E. Ista, A.H. Jonkman, Clinical implementation of advanced respiratory monitoring with esophageal pressure and electrical impedance tomography: results from an international survey and focus group discussion, *Intensive Care Medicine Experimental* 2024 12:1 12 (2024) 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/S40635-024-00686-9>.
- [7] R.S.P. Warnaar, A.D. Cornet, A. Beishuizen, C.M. Moore, D.W. Donker, E. Oppersma, Advanced waveform analysis of diaphragm surface EMG allows for continuous non-invasive assessment of respiratory effort in critically ill patients at different PEEP levels, *Crit Care* 28 (2024) 195. <https://doi.org/10.1186/S13054-024-04978-0>.
- [8] J.J. Wisse, P. Somhorst, J. Behr, A.R. van Nieuw Amerongen, D. Gommers, A.H. Jonkman, Improved filtering methods to suppress cardiovascular contamination in electrical impedance tomography recordings, *Physiol Meas* 45 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6579/AD46E3>.

Section 7: Declaration

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I and all the individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands [Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) (The Universities of the Netherlands).
- The research organisation has been informed of this grant application and the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this programme.
- I have completed this application form truthfully.
- I have submitted a pre-proposal for this Call for proposals in ISAAC.